

SECRECY ASSOCIATION POLICY IN MULTI TIER HETEROGENEOUS NETWORKS

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Abstract:

Network simulator (NS) is an object-oriented, discrete event simulator for networking research. It provides substantial support for simulation of TCP, routing and multicast protocols over wired and wireless networks. An asymptotic analysis of the connection probability reveals that setting a larger access threshold is beneficial for improving link quality and numerically tractable, explicit integral expressions for the distribution of the signal-to-interference-and noise-ratio (SINR) experienced by a typical user in the downlink channel from the k -th strongest base stations of a cellular network modeled by Poisson point process on the plane. Users signal propagation-loss model comprises of a power-law path loss function with arbitrarily distributed shadowing, independent across all base stations, with and without Rayleigh fading. Analyze the network-wide secrecy throughput subject to connection and secrecy probability constraints. To derive the small-antenna and large-antenna cases for the rate of redundant information. To further evaluate the minimum per user secrecy throughput. Then to show that, compared with non-threshold mobile access, the threshold-based policy can significantly increase secrecy throughput when the access threshold is properly chosen.

Index Terms: Secrecy Throughput, Threshold & Link Quality

1. Introduction:

The deployment of heterogeneous cellular networks (HCNs) is a promising approach to providing seamless wireless coverage and high network throughput in 5G mobile communication. A HCN deploys a variety of infrastructure, such as macro, pico, and femto base stations (BSs), as well as fixed relay stations in different tiers. BSs in different tiers have different transmit powers and coverages. For example, a macrocell uses the highest power to provide large coverage, while a femtocell is usually a low-power home BS intended for short-range communications. Due to the co-channel spectrum sharing between different tiers, network interference in the HCN is much more severe than that in a conventional single-tier cellular network, thus posing a challenge to the successful co-existence of tiers. Therefore, one of the major challenges in deploying HCNs is to efficiently manage network interference. Femtocell access control, using either closed or open access, is an important mechanism for interference management. In closed access, femtocell access points provide service only to the specified subscribers, whereas arbitrary nearby users can use the femtocell in open access. Point out that open access is preferred by network operators, since it not only efficiently reduces cross tier interference, but also provides an inexpensive way to expand network capacity. However, due to the open system architecture of a HCN and the broadcast nature of wireless communications, information transmissions intended for authorized user equipments (UEs) are more vulnerable to eavesdroppers (also named unauthorized users). As shown in Fig. 1, eavesdroppers (Eves) find it easy to overhear legitimate communications. Therefore, secure transmission is a significant concern when designing HCNs. Unfortunately, the existing literature on HCNs has mainly focused on network throughput and energy efficiency; little of it has involved security issues. Physical layer security (PLS), or, information-theoretic security, has drawn ever-increasing attention since Wyner's seminal research, where he introduced the degraded wiretap channel model and defined the concept of *secrecy capacity*. During the past decades, the wiretap channel model has been generalized to multi-input multi-output (MIMO) channels, cooperative relay channels, and two-way channels, etc. A large number of secrecy transmission techniques and schemes have been proposed for wireless communications.

A. Related Works and Motivation: Early research on PLS Analyse the connection and secrecy probabilities of the artificial noise-aided secure transmission. A new accurate integral formula as well as an analytically tractable expression for the interference-limited case [1]. PLS has focused on point-to-point links or single-cell scenarios. In some works, Eve's channel state information (CSI) is assumed to be perfectly known at the transmitter, which is clearly not practical in real wiretap scenarios, since Eves are usually passive. Without Eve's CSI, proposed a multi-antenna transmission strategy with artificial noise embedded into information signals to confuse Eve. This method has become a popular approach to enhance the PLS, and has attracted a stream of research. The idea of artificial noise has also been extended to relay systems with jammers, in which cooperative jamming techniques have been proposed to improve PLS. However, due to dynamic and large-scale wireless network topologies, the spatial positions of network nodes and propagation path losses become very critical factors influencing secrecy performance, which unfortunately has been considered by none of the above endeavors. Recently, stochastic

geometry theory has provided a powerful tool to study the average behavior of a network by modeling the positions of network nodes according to a spatial distribution such as a Poisson point process (PPP). Under a stochastic geometry framework, authors in studied the secure multi-antenna transmission against PPP distributed Eves. More specifically, evaluated the secure connectivity of two multi-antenna transmission techniques: a directional antenna scheme and an eigen- beam forming scheme investigated the average secrecy outage probability in a multi-input singleoutput (MISO) wiretap channel for both non-colluding and colluding Eves. Derived the probability of a positive secrecy rate achieved by the artificial-noise method in MIMO channels. Proposed both dynamic and static parameter design schemes for the artificialnoise-aided transmission to maximize secrecy throughput subject to a secrecy outage probability constraint. Research on PLS has been further extended to ad hoc networks and cellular networks where the placement of transmitters and receivers are both modeled as PPPs. Considered single- and multi antenna transmissions in an ad hoc network, and provided a tradeoff analysis between connectivity and secrecy, and further measured the secrecy transmission capacity. Evaluated the secrecy performance of cellular networks considering the cell association and information exchange between BSs, and provided tractable results for the achievable secrecy rate under different assumptions on the information of Eves' locations. However, they only considered a single antenna case, ignoring both small-scale fading and inter-cell interference. This work has been extended by, where investigated the average secrecy rate utilizing the regularized channel inversion transmit recoding from a perspective of massive MIMO systems. Due to the multi-tier hierarchical architecture, HCNs bring new challenges to the investigation of PLS compared with the conventional single-tier topology. In addition to cross-cell interference, HCNs introduce severe cross-tier interference. Both reliability and secrecy of data transmissions should be taken into account, which makes analyzing the impact of interference on both UEs and Eves much more complicated, especially when system parameters differ between different tiers. Besides, mobile terminals can access an arbitrary tier, e.g., open access, which calls for specific mobile association policies that consider both quality of service (QoS) and secrecy. A very recent contribution considered PLS in a two-tier heterogeneous network with one Eve wiretapping macrocell users. We point out that, the authors in focused on the design/optimization of secrecy beamforming, but not from the perspective of network analysis and deployment. Their conclusions are based on the idealized assumption that the CSI of the Eve is perfectly available. Moreover, they considered neither the multi-Eve wiretap scenarios, nor the random spatial positions of network nodes and the large-scale path loss. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has accounted for PLS when designing HCNs, and a fundamental analysis framework to evaluate the secrecy performance in HCNs is lacking, which has motivated our work.

B. Our Work and Contributions: In this paper, we extend PLS to a K -tier HCN where the positions of BSs, UEs and Eves are all modeled as independent homogeneous PPPs. We provide a comprehensive performance analysis of artificial-noise-aided multi-antenna secure transmission under a stochastic geometry framework. Our main contributions are summarized as follows: i) We propose a secrecy mobile association policy based on the *truncated average received signal power* (ARSP). Specifically, a typical UE is only permitted to associate with the BS providing the highest ARSP; if the highest ARSP is below a pre-set access threshold, the UE remains inactive. We derive closed-form expressions for the tier association probability for this policy (the probability that a tier is associated with the typical UE) and the BS activation probability (the probability that a BS associates at least one UE), which are essential to analyze the key performance metrics. ii) We analyze the connection probability of a randomly located UE, which is defined as the probability that the signal to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) of the UE lies above a target SINR. We derive a new accurate integral representation of the connection probability and an analytically tractable expression under the interference-limited case. An asymptotic analysis of the connection probability reveals that setting a larger access threshold is beneficial for improving link quality. iii) We analyze the user secrecy probability, which is defined as the probability that the SINR of an arbitrary Eve lies below a SINR threshold. We derive analytical upper and lower bounds for the secrecy probability, which are close to the exact values in the high secrecy probability region. We find that the access threshold, BS density and power allocation ratio respectively displays a tradeoff between the connection and secrecy probabilities, and that these parameters should be carefully designed to balance link quality and secrecy. iv) We investigate network-wide secrecy throughput subject to connection and secrecy probability constraints. We derive closed-form expressions for the rate of redundant information in small-antenna and large-antenna cases, respectively. We further evaluate the minimum per user secrecy throughput. We show that, compared with non-threshold mobile access, our threshold-based policy can significantly increase secrecy throughout when the access threshold is properly chosen. Leveraging the obtained analytical expressions, we provide various tractable predictions of network performance and guidelines for future network designs. For instance, setting a larger access threshold helps to improve link quality. However, if we aim to increase network-wide secrecy throughput, we should properly choose the access threshold, but not set it as large as possible.

C. Organization and Notations: The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. We describe the system model. We investigate the connection probability and secrecy probability, respectively. We evaluate the network

wide secrecy throughput. We conclude our work. *Notations:* bold uppercase (lowercase) letters denote matrices (column vectors). $(\cdot)^*$, $(\cdot)^T$, $|\cdot|$, $\|\cdot\|$, $P\{\cdot\}$, and $EA(\cdot)$ denote conjugate, transpose, absolute value, Euclidean norm, probability, and expectation with respect to (w.r.t.) A , respectively. $CN(\mu, \sigma^2)$, $\text{Exp}(\lambda)$ and $\Gamma(N, \lambda)$ denote the circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 , exponential distribution with parameter λ , and gamma distribution with parameters N and λ , respectively. $\mathbb{R}_{m \times n}$ and $\mathbb{C}_{m \times n}$ denote the $m \times n$ real and complex number domains, respectively. $\log(\cdot)$ and $\ln(\cdot)$ denote the base-2 and natural logarithms, respectively. $f_V(\cdot)$ and $F_V(\cdot)$ denote the probability density function (PDF) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a random variable V , respectively. $B(o, r)$ describes a disk with center o and radius r . $B^{z,k}$ and $U_x(\text{Ex})$ represent a BS at location z in tier k and a UE (Eve) at location x , respectively. $[x]^+$, $\max(x, 0)$ with x a real number.

2. System Modules:

A. Data Coverage Module: The WiMAX network uses an approach that is similar to that of cell phones. A user sends data from a subscriber device to a base station mounted on a tower or tall building to broadcast the wireless signal in a channel called an uplink, and the base station transmits to the same or other user in a channel called a downlink. Unlike the user, who traditionally has limited resources, i.e. very limited transmission power, limited number of antennas, and limited computation capabilities, the base station can use higher transmission power, more antennas, and enhanced computation algorithms. WiMAX service providers deploy a network of towers that enable access over many miles and the WiMAX broadband service will be available anywhere within coverage areas. Coverage for a geographical area is divided into a series of overlapping areas called cells. When the user travels from one cell to another, the wireless connection is transferred from one cell to another. The signal transmitted from the base station to the user or from the user to the base station through wireless channel faces attenuation in space, fraction, refraction, reflection from objects on the propagation path, and shadowing from walls or other barriers. As a result, the transmitted signal is distorted and sometimes splits into different replicas called multi-paths. The transmitted signal is commonly described by its structure in time, frequency (its frequencies and its bandwidth), and space. The receiver's target at both uplink and downlink is to combat the signal's distortion in order to perfectly recover the transmitted signal and enable reliable data transmission.

Figure 1: Data Coverage Module

B. Data Input Module: IEEE 802.16e-2005 standards construct the basis of Mobile WiMAX Physical (PHY) Layer and Medium Access Layer (MAC). 802.16 series defines five Wireless Metropolitan Area Networks (Wireless MAN) PHY layers and any of them can be combined with the MAC layer. In Fig 3, a detailed view of protocol layer structure of mobile WiMAX system profile is presented from the air interface perspective. Wireless MAN-SC is the first standard that is introduced by the 802.16 working group. It employs a single-carrier (SC) line-of-sight (LOS) modulation for point-to-point communication to operate in the 10-66 GHz spectrum. This standard is to address network access support to buildings with data rates that is comparable to those offered by high-speed fiber optic networks.. Wireless MAN-SCA is the second amendment to the 802.16 standard. LOS communication in SC is ratified with 802.16a-2003 amendment to address low frequency 2-11 GHz spectrum with non-line-of-sight (NLOS) point-to-multipoint communication for fixed broadband wireless access. The 802.16a-2003 added an OFDM PHY, which is called Wireless MAN- OFDM, with 256 subcarriers to accommodate NLOS fixed access for frequencies in 2-11 GHz. Later, it is finalized in 802.16-2004 standards. This is the approved WiMAX fixed access standard by WiMAX Forum. The 802.16a is up to 2048-carrier OFDMA PHY to accommodate NLOS point-to-multipoint communication, which is Wireless MAN-OFDMA. This is ratified in 802.16-2004 and revisited in 802.16e-2005 for mobile access.

Figure 2: Layer Structure

Figure 3: Data Aggregate

Figure 4: Identify the Conspiracy Attack

Figure 5: Robust Data Aggregation

Figure 6: Iterative Filtering

C. Scalable OFDMA: OFDMA is the multiple access technique for mobile WiMAX. OFDMA is the Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) based multiple access schemes and has become the single choice for modern broadband wireless technologies adopted in other competing technologies such as 3GPP's Long Term Evolution (LTE) and 3GPP2's Ultra Mobile Broadband (UMB). OFDMA demonstrates superior performance in non-line-of-sight (NLOS) multi-path channels with its relatively simple transceiver structures and allows efficient use of the available spectrum resources by time and frequency sub channelization. The simple transceiver structure of OFDMA also enables feasible implementation of advanced antenna techniques such as MIMO with reasonable complexity. Last, OFDMA employed in mobile WiMAX is scalable in the sense that by flexibly adjusting FFT sizes and channel bandwidths with fixed symbol duration and subcarrier spacing, it can address various spectrum needs in different regional regulations in a cost competitive manner. The bandwidth adjustment can be chosen between 1.25-20MHz. The scalability is realized with FFT size variation and the frequency spacing of sub-carriers is defined to be 10.94 kHz.

D. Time Division Duplex (TDD) Frame Structure: The mobile WiMAX Release 1 (WiMAX R-1) Profile has only TDD as the duplexing mode even though the baseline IEEE standards contain both TDD and Frequency Division Duplex (FDD). Even though future WiMAX Releases will have FDD mode as well, TDD is in many ways better positioned for mobile Internet services than FDD. First of all, Internet traffic is asymmetric typically with the amount of downlink traffic exceeding the amount of uplink traffic; thus, conventional FDD with the same downlink and uplink channel bandwidth does not provide the optimum use of resources. With TDD products, operators are capable of adjusting downlink and uplink ratios based on their service needs in the networks. In addition, TDD is inherently better suited to more advanced antenna techniques such as Adaptive Antenna System (AAS) or Beam forming (BF) than FDD due to the channel reciprocity between the uplink and downlink. Mobile Internet with increased multimedia services naturally requires the use of advanced antenna techniques to improve capacity and coverage.

Figure 7: OFDMA Frame Structure in TDD

In Fig 7, the downlink sub frame begins with a downlink preamble that is used for PHY layer procedures, such as time and frequency synchronization and initial channel estimation. The downlink preamble is followed by a frame **control** header (FCH), which provides frame configuration information, such as the MAP message length, the modulation, and coding scheme, and the usable subcarriers. Multiple users are allocated data regions within the frame, and these allocations are specified in the uplink and downlink MAP messages (DL-MAP and UL-MAP) that are broadcast following the FCH in the downlink sub frame. MAP messages include the burst profile for each user, which defines the modulation and coding scheme used in that link. Since MAP contains critical information that needs to reach all users, it is often sent over a very reliable link, such as binary phase shift key (BPSK) with rate 1/2 coding and repetition coding. Although the MAP messages are an elegant way for the base station to inform the various users of its allocations and burst profiles on a per-frame basis, it could form a significant overhead, particularly when there are a large number of users with small packets for which allocations need to be specified. To mitigate the overhead concern, mobile WiMAX systems can optionally use multiple sub-MAP messages where the dedicated control messages to different users are transmitted at higher rates, based on their individual Signal-Interference-Noise Ratio (SINR) conditions. The broadcast MAP messages may also optionally be compressed for additional efficiency.

E. Data Addressing: The primary task of the WiMAX MAC layer is to provide an interface between the higher transport layers and the physical layer. The MAC layer takes packets from the upper layer that is called MAC service data units (SDU) and organizes them into MAC protocol data units (PDU) for transmission over the air. For received transmissions, the MAC layer does the reverse. The IEEE 802.16-2004 and IEEE 802.16e-2005 MAC design includes a convergence sub layer that can interface with a variety of higher layer protocols, such as ATM, Ethernet, IP, and adaptable for future protocol. The WiMAX MAC uses a variable length PDU and offers a lot of flexibility to allow for their efficient transmission. For example, multiple PDUs of same or different lengths may be aggregated into a single burst to save PHY overhead. Similarly, multiple SDUs from the higher layer service may be concatenated into a single PDU to save MAC header overhead. Conversely, large SDUs may be fragmented into smaller PDUs and sent across multiple frames.

3. Conclusions:

This comprehensively studies the PLS of HCNs where the locations of all BSs, UEs and Eves are modeled as independent homogeneous PPPs. We first propose a mobile association policy based on the truncated ARSP and derive the tier association and BS activation probabilities. We then analyze the connection and secrecy probabilities of the artificial noise-aided secure transmission. For connection probability, we provide a new accurate integral formula as well as an analytically tractable expression for the interference-

limited case. For secrecy probability, we obtain closed-form expressions for both upper and lower bounds, which are approximate to the exact values at the high secrecy probability regime. Constrained by the connection and secrecy probabilities, we evaluate the network-wide secrecy throughput and also the minimum secrecy throughput per user.

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